

On the interpretation of utterances with expressive expletives

Abstract

Expressive adjectives or *expressive expletives* have been argued to voice the speaker's attitude towards the referent of the noun with which they co-occur, even though the attitude may be felt to be expressed about the referent of another sentential constituent or the state of affairs alluded to in the sentence where they are inserted. A previous pragmatic approach suggests that this is possible because these expletives perform an individual speech act, while a syntactic approach posits a feature whose detachment from a particular constituent enables the speaker's attitude to target the referent of another sentential constituent or even on the entire proposition expressed. This paper proposes an alternative relevance-theoretic account of the interpretation of utterances containing expressive expletives, which considers pragmatic factors and the cognitive processes in comprehension. It is grounded in contributions on the output of lexical pragmatic processes and the role of paralinguistic clues in utterance comprehension.

Keywords: Relevance Theory, expressive adjectives/expletives, speaker's attitude, speech-act hypothesis, expressive feature, argument hopping, attitudinal representations, ad hoc concepts, paralinguistic, higher-level explicatures

1 Introduction

Expressives make up a rather heterogeneous group that includes *expressive adjectives* (Blakemore 2011, 2015): i.e., words like 'fucking', 'damn(ed)' or 'bleeding'. Although they have constantly aroused much interest, studies have concentrated on cross-generational and gender variation in their use in a number of contexts (Staley 1978; De Klerk 1981; Hughes 1992; McCloskey & Coleman 1992; Bayard & Krishnayya 2001;

Kaye & Sapolsky 2004; Jay 2005; Murphy 2009) and delved into their solidarity-signalling and androgynous values (Hopper et al. 1980; Daly et al. 2004). In relevance-theoretic pragmatics attention has been paid to how such items communicate and what they contribute to communication (Author 2018a, 2019). However, there remain unsettled a series of issues concerning the attitude that the speaker expresses.

Reportedly, an expressive adjective that is appended to the head of a noun phrase may be considered to voice the speaker's attitude towards its referent, the referent of another nominal head or even the entire proposition expressed, among others. An extant pragmatic approach surmises that this is possible because the expressive adjective accomplishes an independent speech act (Frazier, Dillon & Clifton 2015). Although this attitudinal target variability depends on satisfaction of certain conditions, a subsequent syntactic approach denies the possibility that the referent of a distinct sentence constituent, or even the state of affairs alluded to in a whole sentence, is the target of the attitude expressed by the speaker (Guztman 2019). Yet, a recent empirical study adduces non-conclusive evidence about the possible targets of the attitude that expressive adjectives verbalise (Bross 2021).

This paper revisits these two approaches with a view to accounting for the interpretation of utterances containing these adjectives from a pragmatic perspective. This account rests squarely on relevance-theoretic pragmatics (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995; Wilson & Sperber 2002, 2004) and, more precisely, on the role played in comprehension by certain linguistic and paralinguistic elements, whose understanding has greatly benefitted from the work done by Deirdre Wilson. As a cognitive-pragmatic model centred on understanding, relevance theory is well equipped and suited for offering psychologically plausible solutions to an array of problems. Its cornerstone is the notion of *relevance*, which is defined on the basis of two factors: *cognitive effect* or

knowledge gain, and *cognitive or processing effort*. Effort considerations, on the one hand, will be argued to be essential for refuting some of the claims made by the extant approaches and for searching for an alternative account.

On the other hand, relevance theory posits a model of comprehension in which linguistic and paralinguistic input set in motion a sophisticated mental machinery that performs a variety of parallel processes that are fundamental for arriving at the speaker's meaning: decoding, pragmatic enrichment of the decoded logical form through disambiguation, reference assignment, lexical pragmatic processes resulting in specified concepts, recovery of unarticulated constituents and/or establishment of various logical relationships between information items, representation of the speaker's attitude or of the action that she attempts to perform through her words, and deduction of implicit contents (Carston 2000, 2002; Wilson & Sperber 2002, 2004).¹ Lexical items like expressive adjectives, which will be here regarded as *expletives*, certainly assist some of these processes and determine their outputs, but so do other linguistic items and paralinguistic clues. The proposal made in this paper is based on relevance-theoretic contributions about such items and clues.

This paper continues by summarising the major claims made by the extant approaches to the interpretation of the words under scrutiny. Next, it explains some of their drawbacks and justifies the need for a pragmatic, relevance-theoretic account. After introducing the basic notions and mental processes distinguished in relevance theory, the paper offers this account. To conclude, it makes some final remarks and suggestions for future research.

¹ Following a relevance-theoretic convention, reference to the speaker will be made through the feminine third person singular personal pronoun, while reference to the hearer will be made through the masculine counterpart.

2 Expressive expletives and attitude expression

Seeming adjectives and present and past participles like ‘damn(ed)’, ‘fucking’ or ‘bleeding’ can often modify the head of noun phrases in languages like English:

(1) My friend has invited his *damn(ed)* girlfriend.

Although such words are often labelled ‘expressive adjectives’ (Potts 2007a; Frazier, Dillon & Clifton 2015; Gutzmann 2019; Bross 2021), their non-adjectival nature is evident by the fact that they do not denote stable or scalar qualities enabling them to qualify or specify nominal referents. They cannot be intensified or gradated, or receive prefixes, either. Furthermore, their placement in predicative position or replacement by a defining relative clause, albeit possible, dramatically alters the sentence meaning (Huddleston 1988; Greenbaum & Quirk 1993; Haegeman & Guéron 1999; Collins & Hollo 2000; Börjars & Burridge 2001). These words verbalise something very elusive, and somewhat ineffable: the speaker’s attitudes, feelings and/or emotions. Along with some epithets, slurs, interjections, pitch, tones and gestures, they certainly fall within the broader category of expressives (Potts 2007a, 2007b; Blakemore 2011, 2015).

However, the elusiveness and ineffability of what they communicate also rank them on a par with other semantically-empty items such as the existential ‘there’ or the slot-filler ‘it’. These are considered expletives, and so may be the lexical items under consideration. Accordingly, they may alternatively be termed *expressive expletives* (Author, In press a).

Expressive expletives do not contribute to the truth-conditional content of utterances of the sentences where they occur. If they are embedded into a conditional structure, they do not fall within the scope of the conditional operator. Thus, embedding (1) into that sort of structure (2a) would involve that the state of affairs alluded to in the main clause might hold true provided (2b) applied, but not in the case (2c) was true:

- (2) a. If my friend has invited his damned girlfriend, I will not join the party.
b. My friend has invited his girlfriend.
c. My friend has invited a girlfriend who is damned.

Yet, eliminating expressive expletives erases information about the speaker's attitude, emotion or feelings. These cannot be denied, challenged or questioned (Potts 2005: 158), but a dissenting opinion may be expressed about the words employed to verbalise them:

- (3) a. Do not say that she is a damned girlfriend!
b. Do not call her a damned girlfriend!

An issue that has raised much speculation is the actual target of the speaker's feelings or emotions (Potts 2005; Frazier, Dillon & Clifton 2015; Gutzmann 2019; Bross 2021). Admittedly, in a transitive sentence like (1) it would be the direct object, as it is immediately preceded by the expressive expletive. However, there are other, albeit surprising, possibilities. One is the referent of a constituent different from that which the expletive overtly modifies: the subject. Consequently, the expressive 'hops' linearly, in this case to the left. Gutzmann (2019) calls this phenomenon *argument*

hopping and this particular case *left hopping*. Conversely, if the expletive accompanied the subject constituent and was considered to convey a negative emotion about the object, that would be a case of *right hopping*:

(4) My damn(ed) friend has invited her girlfriend.

A further possibility is that the speaker's psychological state concerned the whole state of affairs described by the sentence. This would involve a *sentence-level interpretation* and require *argument extension*. Still, if the sentence where the expressive expletive occurs was subordinated to a matrix clause (5), it could be felt that the negative attitude that the expletive verbalises is held towards the referent of the matrix-subject—i.e., *matrix-subject interpretation*—or towards the entire content expressed by the complex clause—i.e., *matrix-clause interpretation*—even though the expletive appeared in the embedded clause (Bross 2021):²

(5) Peter said that my friend has invited his damn(ed) girlfriend.

An extant pragmatic approach posits that expressive expletives make up a quasi-independent speech act conveying not-at-issue content, which is distinct from the rest of a sentence conveying at-issue content (Frazier, Dillon & Clifton 2015). This semi-independence makes it possible for an expletive of this type to express emotions about different sentence constituents or even a whole sentence. Based on work by Potts (2005, 2007a), this account is known as the *speech-act hypothesis*. It also contends that the

² Theoretically, it could also be possible that the attitude voiced through an expressive expletive occurring in a matrix clause may be sensed to be expressed about a constituent in an embedded clause, so the expletive would hop from the matrix into the embedded (Gutzman 2019).

likelihood of perceiving that the negative attitude has been expressed about a subject constituent also depends on the agentive-causer nature of the referent of this constituent. This is the *culprit hypothesis*: if the subject denotes an individual who can be held responsible for an action, as in (6a), that constituent will very likely be the target of the attitude conveyed by the expressive expletive, regardless of the actual position of the expletive. In contrast, if the subject does not allude to an individual that may be the agent of an action, as in (6b), it will not be the target of the speaker's attitude:³

(6) a. My friend invited his damn(ed) girlfriend.

b. The holiday is on the damn weekend. (from Frazier, Dillon & Clifton 2015)

This approach is questioned from a syntactic perspective, however. A matrix-clause interpretation is ruled out when expressive expletives occur inside an embedded clause because a syntactic barrier prevents them from taking within their scope the matrix clause or any of its constituents (Gutzmann 2019).⁴ Therefore, expressive expletives could only have local, argument-hopping or sentence-level interpretations. In other words, one might only see the attitude that they voice as being held towards the referent of the constituent they co-occur with, that of another constituent within the embedded clause or the state of affairs referred to in the entire embedded clause. Yet, interpretations requiring argument hopping are also syntactically illicit due to a syntactic *expressivity feature*.

³ Frazier, Dillon and Clifton (2015) adduce empirical evidence supporting both the speech act and the culprit hypotheses: 48 undergraduate students considered expressive expletives to convey a negative attitude towards the state of affairs alluded to in a sentence irrespective of whether the expletive preceded the subject or object constituents, and reported more subject interpretations when the subject was an agentive causer.

⁴ Gutzmann (2019) also presents supportive empirical evidence consisting of responses by 60 undergraduate students who judged root and embedded clauses with an expressive expletive that modified the subject or the direct object.

According to Gutzmann (2019), expressive expletives carry this feature, so they automatically receive a local interpretation before a nominal head. For an argument-hopping reading to be licensed, the feature would need to be detached from the expletive and be attached, in a first step, to the head of a determiner phrase, just to be subsequently deleted. This would enable the feature to move higher up in the syntactic structure while retaining a *c-command relation* with the expletive. Consequently, interpretations requiring argument hopping would allegedly arise only provided a sentence-level interpretation is active; however, such interpretations would not be syntactically motivated, but could solely arise as implicatures (Gutzmann 2019: 107). In fact, a sentence-level interpretation may be impeded by the addition of a semantically-opposed attitudinal adverbial, thus rendering odd an interpretation contingent on argument hopping (7):

(7) *Fortunately*, my friend invited his damn(ed) girlfriend.

Quite recently, Bross (2021) has tested the predictions made in both the pragmatic and the syntactic approaches concerning the feasibility of readings involving argument hopping or crossing syntactic barriers.⁵ Unfortunately, his results are not conclusive: interpretations requiring argument hopping were possible for approximately 50% of the participants in his study and the matrix clause reading was assessed plausible by almost 60% of the participants, but the matrix-subject interpretation was only judged acceptable by 30% of the participants. This suggests that the conclusion about the role of syntactic blockage is excessive. Moreover, his findings do not indicate that “there are

⁵ His study recruited 83 students of German who subscribed to a mailing list.

generally no syntactic mechanisms involved”, but that “there are pragmatic mechanisms at work which have been overlooked so far” (Bross 2021: 12).

Not only have the pragmatic and syntactic approaches not paid heed to the pragmatic mechanisms that may intervene in the interpretation of the utterances of sentences where expletive expressives appear, but they also ignore the role of further linguistic items and paralinguistic clues in utterance production and interpretation, above all when it comes to the expression of psychological states. While the pragmatic approach is anchored in the idea that the speaker may be performing two independent verbal actions by means of the sentence where an expressive expletive occurs, as well as on characteristics of the subject referent, the syntactic approach assumes that a syntactic feature may restrict the sentential constituents whose referents are amenable to being the targets of the attitude that the speaker verbalises through an expressive expletive. Yet, were such possibilities feasible, they would demand a considerable amount of cognitive effort. Additionally, both approaches also suffer from certain weaknesses that detract from psychological plausibility. The next section discusses them in more detail.

3 Some problems with the extant approaches

The pragmatic and the syntactic approaches assume that expressive expletives are the means to display the speaker’s attitude and that it may be expressed about the referents of different sentence constituents irrespective of their position within the sentence. However, neither approach explains what this involves in cognitive, representational terms. To put it differently, none of the approaches makes it clear whether a mental representation of the expressed attitude needs to be entertained and, if so, what the

format and status of that representation is. Were these expletives admitted to trigger it, it might be thought to take within its scope just a conceptual component in a pragmatically enriched propositional form. Allegedly, this could justify differentiating that representation from a higher-order conceptual schema capturing the action that the speaker performs through the utterance of a sentence or her psychological state about the proposition expressed, which in relevance-theoretic pragmatics is known as the *higher-level explicature* (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995; Wilson & Sperber 2002, 2004; more on this below). Owing to the shorter-ranging scope of that new attitudinal representation, it could be termed *intermediate-level explicature* (Author 2018a).

However, the enactment of this additional attitudinal representation may be psychologically burdensome and perhaps unlikely, above all given that the evolution of the human mind and the processing tasks that it performs have been prompted by an optimisation of resources and effort investment (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995).

Intuitively, the construction of such a representation would increase the number of tasks that the mind realises during *mutual parallel adjustment* (Carston 2000, 2002; Sperber & Wilson 2002, 2004), the variety of representations with which it would work and, ultimately, the amount of cognitive effort. And, as long as such increases obviously hamper cognitive efficiency, they would seem unwarranted (Author 2020a). Perhaps the representation of the psychological states about the referents of certain words endowed with conceptual content does not need to be accomplished through a further independent cognitive entity, but may be contingent on, and be a consequence of, some other pragmatic process (Author, In press a).

A second problem of the extant pragmatic and syntactic approaches concerns the claim that the attitude that the speaker exhibits may be held towards the referent of a syntactic constituent other than the one modified by an expressive expletive, or even

towards a state of affairs alluded to in a sentence. In so doing, both approaches appear to ignore the role of a number of linguistic and paralinguistic elements in the communication of attitudinal information and tacitly assume a functional overlap with some of them. Among the former group of elements feature interjections and attitudinal adverbials, while the latter include prosodic features like tone, pitch or tempo, and visual clues like gestures, facial expressions, poses or movements. Although all of them serve a common purpose—namely, conveying information about the speaker’s psychological state—their respective scopes differ and hence their processing outputs too. Moreover, the judgements made by the participants in the studies by Frazier, Dillon and Clifton (2015), Gutzmann (2019) and Bross (2021) regarding the readings supposedly involving argument hopping and argument extension might have been motivated by putative readings or interpretations where elements from said groups of elements could have been unconsciously considered. This might have caused the participants to feel that the speaker’s attitude was expressed towards a constituent other than the one adjacent to an expressive expletive or the whole proposition where it occurred.

Furthermore, the fact that an expressive expletive precedes a particular constituent, while the speaker actually intends to express her attitude about the referent of another non-adjacent constituent and the hearer ends up grasping this, apart from appearing somewhat awkward, would intuitively contravene a fundamental presumption in communication: that *competent*—i.e., with an adequate command of their language—and *benevolent*—i.e., trustworthy—speakers will aim at optimal relevance and, on the grounds of their goals and linguistic abilities, will formulate their verbal contributions in a manner that straightforwardly and effortlessly directs hearers to the intended interpretation (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995; Sperber 1994). In other words, placement

of an expressive expletive next to a constituent whose reference is not the intended target of an attitude would not make the speaker's *informative intention* manifest in the most efficient and least effort-demanding manner (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995). If the speaker aimed to show a negative attitude towards, say, the referent of the subject of a sentence, why would she attach the expletive to the object? Wouldn't it be much clearer to display her attitude towards its referent by directly modifying the subject constituent with the expletive? Were the expletive placed by the object constituent, wouldn't interpreting that the speaker has a particular attitude towards the subject referent demand more processing effort? Wouldn't that placement be misleading and eventually conducive to misunderstanding (Author 2013, 2017, 2020b)? In fact, the hearer could think that the expletive was misplaced and, depending on his condescendence, perhaps eventually conclude that the speaker is an unskilled communicator, which may ultimately encourage him to sustain a *pragmatic competence injustice* against her (Author 2018b). Arguably, it seems more common-sensical, less effort-demanding and more likely to contribute to optimal relevance that the addition of an expressive expletive to a noun phrase overtly indicates that the attitude that the speaker wishes to voice is about the referent of its head.

Still, a further problem originates in the way in which both approaches justify the relative 'mobility' of the attitude verbalised by expressive expletives. The pragmatic approach postulates that these expletives are part of a subsidiary speech act that coexists with the core speech act that the speaker realises by means of the utterance of the sentence hosting them (Frazier, Dillon & Clifton 2015). Although computing the two verbal acts may require the additional cognitive effort to create their respective representations, it seems more logical to assume that the speaker simply performs one and that information about her attitude towards something mentioned is somehow

integrated in its mental representation. In turn, the syntactic approach resorts to a feature whose activation, detachment from a syntactic constituent and attachment to a distinct one must somehow be monitored (Gutzmann 2019). As in the case of the overt or covert indexicals, or the empty constituent slots hypothesised in other accounts to explain the recovery of unarticulated constituents (Recanati 1989; Stanley 2000, 2002), that feature may be superfluous or redundant, whereas its movements up the syntactic tree might not actually take place or even be needed for hearers to decide on the referent of the constituent towards which the speaker holds a particular attitude. Rather, a hearer may simply conclude that the speaker expresses that attitude towards the referent of the constituent next to which the expletive appears, but that she simultaneously holds a similar attitude towards the referent of another constituent as a consequence of the co-occurrence of other linguistic elements and paralinguistic clues. They would play a major role in comprehension by assisting hearers in the recovery of attitudinal information about the referent of that other constituent.

Finally, if the mind really kept track of the syntactic feature linked to expressive expletives and blocked some of its movements, as the syntactic approach argues (Gutzmann 2019), a new problem would emerge. The assumption that the speaker has a certain attitude towards the referent of a constituent other than the one by which it occurs would arise as an implicature. Little is said about the content and format of that implicit content too, but the syntactic approach seems to presuppose that all implicatures are equal and involve a propositional representation. However, when it comes to intangible and fairly subjective things like emotions, attitudes or feelings, it seems more likely that processing the items showing or verbalising them yields outputs that are still evasive and lack a propositional format (Wilson & Wharton 2006; Wharton 2009, 2012, 2016; Wilson & Carston 2019). Moreover, perhaps deriving an implicature

about the speaker's psychological state is more demanding in cognitive terms than obtaining information about it through other mental operations triggered by diverse elements in the input.

Undeniably, a comprehensive account of the various attitude-related phenomena in utterances of sentences containing expressive expletives, as Bross (2021) aptly points out, needs to seriously consider pragmatic factors and the cognitive mechanisms operating in comprehension. Such an account must solve the actual role of expressive expletives and whether the attitude that they evidence can be extended to the referent of other constituents or to the state of affairs alluded to in the proposition expressed. If this were proven to not be licensed, that account needs to clarify how the speaker can indicate that the referent of another constituent or the state of affairs in that proposition also become the target of her attitude, and what the hearer's mind needs to do in order to understand this. Certainly, that account may be grounded in relevance theory, as it provides the notional apparatus and describes the comprehension process in a psychologically plausible way. The next section introduces some of the basic concepts and processes on which such an account relies and then presents it.

4 Towards a relevance-theoretic account

In addition to a definition of relevance based on cognitive gain and cognitive investment, relevance theory rests squarely on a general principle that is claimed to govern cognition—"Human cognition tends to be geared to the maximisation of relevance" (Sperber & Wilson 1995: 260)—and another more specific principle that governs communication, and hence comprehension: "Every act of ostensive

communication communicates a presumption of its own optimal relevance” (Sperber & Wilson 1995: 260). This presumption means, according to Sperber and Wilson (1995: 270), that an overtly-produced intentional stimulus like an utterance will somehow compensate the cognitive effort that the hearer will need to dedicate to processing it by means of a certain amount of cognitive effects—strengthening of previous information, contradiction and eventual rejection of old information, and derivation of new information—and that such a stimulus will do so on the grounds of the speaker’s abilities—i.e., her *communicative competence* (Author 2017)—and preferences—i.e., her communicative goals (Mazzarella 2013).

Relevance theory also characterises verbal comprehension as an exercise in mindreading during which the mind decodes the linguistic signal and monitors paralinguistic input, constructs a chunk of variables and conceptual representations, and enriches it through a number of subconscious, incredibly fast inferential tasks. These normally follow the path demanding the least cognitive effort possible and stop when an output is reached that satisfies expectations of relevance: when effort expenditure is felt to have been offset by enough cognitive benefit. Besides disambiguation, reference assignment, recovery of unarticulated constituents and establishment of certain relations between the states of affairs alluded to by the speaker, one of such tasks is conceptual adjustment (Carston 2000, 2002; Wilson & Carston 2006, 2007).

The conceptual representations in the chunks constructed by the mind are activated by words encoding *conceptual meaning*—i.e., content or open class words—and amount to some sort of raw material that needs to be modulated or specified on the basis of contextual information, among which are preceding utterances, the cotext and perceptible information. Two types of adjustments are differentiated in relevance theory: *narrowing*, or delimiting the denotation of a concept towards a more specific

notional space, and *broadening*, or loosening its denotation towards a less specific notional space. Accordingly, interpreting (8a) below requires that the hearer restricts the concept CHEESE as denoting a particular type or brand, or perhaps cheese with a specific flavour or texture, or cut in a certain manner, thus creating the idiosyncratic concept CHEESE*.⁶ In turn, interpreting (8b) below requires him to deprive ROUND of some quintessential, defining property like absolute, perfect roundness in order to construct ROUND*:

- (8) a. Susan usually has cheese as a snack.
b. Picadilly Circus is round.

The result of these adjustments are *ad hoc concepts* or occasion-specific, context-sensitive, and perhaps highly idiosyncratic, conceptual entities. However, these adjustments are not mutually exclusive, but may be simultaneously needed in order to understand intended meaning. This is the case of metaphorical utterances, where the resulting fine-tuned concept is both narrower and looser than the initial concept literally encoded by a word. Thus, adjusting STAR as STAR* when interpreting (9) below would involve eliminating some prototypical attributes of a star that are connected with fame, prestige, skilfulness, success or public recognition, for instance, while delimiting the kind of stardom whereby a person may be qualified as a star.⁷

- (9) Martha is a star!

⁶ According to another relevance-theoretic convention, concepts are notated in small caps and the output of their adjustment is followed by a superscripted asterisk or star.

⁷ A more radical relevance-theoretic approach to ad hoc-concept construction contends that it does not involve adjustments of denotational content, but creation of occasion-specific, context-sensitive conceptual material as a result of the procedures encoded by the so-called content words. Such a material would be some sort of mental file amenable to storing varied information (Carston 2013a, 2013b; Wilson 2016).

Although ad hoc-concept construction has often been presented as an automatic lexical pragmatic process (Carston 2000; Jary 2016), the need for it may be overtly signalled, and its output may even be steered, by a series of elements. On the one hand, there are paralinguistic elements like interjections, prosodic clues like pitch, lexical and contrastive stress, and tempo, and visual clues like the *language-like gestures*—i.e., gestures that are integrated into a linguistic string—*pantomimes*—i.e., movements depicting objects or actions—and *emblems*—i.e., culture-specific gestures conveying idiosyncratic meanings (Author, In press b).⁸ On the other hand, there are linguistic elements like the diminutive and augmentative morphemes, determiners, demonstratives and adjectives, as well as stylistic choices involving lexical items, such as repetition or reformulation (Scott 2019; Author 2020a, Submitted). Elements like expletives may indicate, trigger and direct this process, too (Author, In press a). Since it involves modifications and rearrangements in the information stored in the *logical entry* and/or the *encyclopaedic entry* of a concept (Carston 2000, 2002; Wilson & Carston 2006, 2007; Hall 2017),⁹ expressive expletives could be thought to make manifest attitudinal information that is likely to find a place among the informational storage of the concept activated by the lexical item that they accompany.

Other tasks performed during comprehension is attributing attitudes, emotions or feelings to the speaker and representing them. These may be held towards an entire communicated proposition, which the hearer entertains as a pragmatically enriched form, or the *lower-level explicature* of an utterance (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995), and may be made manifest by an array of linguistic elements like attitudinal adverbials—

⁸ These labels come from the classifications of gestures made by Kendon (1988) and McNeill (1992).

⁹ While the logical information of a concept includes the defining, prototypical properties of what it denotes, its encyclopaedic entry subsumes personal or cultural information associated with its denotation (Sperber & Wilson 1995: 88-89).

e.g., *happily*, *sadly*, etc. (Ifantidou 1992)—and paralinguistic elements like interjections—e.g., *alas!*, *wow!*, etc. (Wharton 2003, 2009; Author 2009a, 2009b)—and prosodic clues like intonation, gestures and facial expressions (Wilson & Wharton 2006; Wharton 2009, 2012). But psychological states may also be experienced about the referent of conceptual elements and be voiced through a variety of elements. Linguistic elements comprise the diminutive and augmentative morphemes, determiners and demonstratives (Author, In press a, b), while paralinguistic ones include interjections, pitch, contrastive stress, tempo, language-like gestures, pantomimes and emblems (Author, Submitted). Obviously, expletive expressives belong to the former group. Like these varied elements, expressive expletives would give rise to representations of information about the attitudes, emotions or feelings that the speaker expresses, even though, for the aforementioned reasons, such representations would not amount to some sort of intermediate-level explicature.

It is on the basis of recent relevance-theoretic work on the elements enacting and directing lexical pragmatic processes and those facilitating representation of psychological states that an alternative account will henceforth be proposed. It attempts to solve the following issues:

- What do expressive expletives communicate and what are their actual effects in processing terms?
- Why may the speaker's attitudes be perceived to have been expressed about the referent(s) of constituent(s) other than the one an expressive expletive modifies?
- Why may the speaker's attitude be felt as being voiced about the state of affairs referred to in the sentence where the expressive expletive appears?

Addressing these issues involves considering other linguistic and paralinguistic elements that certainly play a major role in attitude expression and representation.

4.1 On the contribution of expressive expletives to communication

Two facts reveal that expressive expletives communicate the speaker's attitudes towards the referent of the word they are appended to: on the one hand, their adnominal position and integration within the noun phrase headed by that word; on the other hand, the fact that in inflectional languages like Spanish or Italian, in which there is grammatical gender agreement, expletive expressives agree with the noun they modify in terms of gender:

(10)a. El puto/jodido imbécil ha roto la ventana.

‘The fucking jerk has broken the window’.

b. La dichosa reunión terminó muy tarde.

‘The damn(ed) meeting ended very late’.

However, concerning the output of their processing, rather than triggering an independent representation capturing the speaker's attitude about that referent, it could seem more plausible that these expletives may enact ad hoc-concept construction and thus contribute to fine-tuning the denotational content activated by the head of the noun phrase in which they are integrated as modifiers. Since such an adjustment involves rearranging the information that is already stored within the logical and encyclopaedic entries of a concept, or addition of new one (Carston 2000, 2002; Wilson & Carston 2006, 2007; Hall 2017), these expletives would make manifest information about the speaker's attitude, which will immediately be hosted by such entries of the concept activated by the word that they accompany. Indeed, like interjections and some facial

expressions and gestures, expressive expletives overtly and intentionally *show* the speaker's psychological states by providing somewhat direct evidence of them. Moreover, their lexical nature enables them to be conventionally associated with (certain) psychological states, so they are endowed with *non-natural meaning* about them and communicate by means of *saying* (Grice 1957; Wharton 2001, 2002; Author 2018a).

This hybrid mode of communicating helps speakers make their informative intention rather determinate and causes the interpretation of expressive expletives to be contingent on both decoding and a considerable amount of inferential work (Sperber & Wilson 2015). Yet, the information that they make manifest does not need to have a propositional format or amount to a small set of identifiable propositions. Like interjections, facial expressions and gestures, expressive expletives set in motion a series of perceptual, emotional or sensorimotor mechanisms specialised in reading and attributing emotions. Hence, their output may be an unlimited set of propositions and even non-propositional, but sensorimotor, representations including images, feelings or mental states, whose actual import and manifold shades, such as type, vividness, intensity or authenticity, cannot be precisely paraphrased (Wilson & Carston 2019: 32-36). Accordingly, expressive expletives somehow indicate the direction where the speaker's intended meaning is to be searched, thus fulfilling a signalling function concerning the type of intended emotional or attitudinal content that she expresses irrespective of its actual format. Following recent work by Madella (2020), this function, added to the semantic emptiness of expressive expletives, warrants that they work as an assistive *ostensive pointing* linguistic device (Author, Submitted).

The assumptions or beliefs and the (wide array of) non-propositional information that expressive expletives very likely make manifest may be thought to contribute to

narrowing the conceptual content of the word adjacent to them, thus giving rise to a highly idiosyncratic, occasion-specific conceptual representation where such information would find a place within its logical and/or encyclopaedic entries. To put it differently, expressive expletives may play a major role in the lexical pragmatic processes carried out during mutual parallel adjustment and steer them in such a way that their by-product includes emotion- or attitude-related information. Owing to their semantic emptiness, they may be considered *procedural* elements—i.e., items encoding processing, computational instructions (Blakemore 1987, 1992, 2002; Wilson & Sperber 1993)—which set constraints on the direction that the conceptual adjustment of the lexical item they co-occur with should take, as well as on the sort of information that it should rely on (Author, In press a). The elusiveness and ineffability of what expressive expletives communicate would deprive them of a concrete conceptual content, or perhaps make them simply encode some sort of very broad or vague content and enable them to encode a *procedure* that causes the representation and storage of varied propositional and non-propositional information pertaining to the speaker's psychological states within the logical and/or encyclopaedic entries of the concept activated by an adjacent term. This involves that such types of information may be entertained as a consequence of the utterance of these expletives, even if they are filed in one of the entries of an ensuing conceptual entity.

Accordingly, 'damn(ed)' in (1) above would fine-tune GIRLFRIEND in such a way that the resulting concept GIRLFRIEND* homes in its logical and/or encyclopaedic entries assumptions concerning the antipathy, scorn, disrespect, anger, etc., which the speaker is perceived to feel about the person in question; beliefs about the degree, authenticity, intensity or vividness of the speaker's feelings; her disagreeable, contemptuous, rude, furious, etc., attitude towards that person; a wide array of ineffable negative emotions

and/or shades of them which that person causes her to experience, and/or perhaps even specific indescribable images about a particular sort of fiancé. All that information contributes to the specification of the descriptive content activated by the noun by which the expletive is located, so it would be part and parcel of a conceptual component of the proposition that the speaker explicitly communicates. It may be true or false in its own right, but it does not impact the truth conditions of that proposition. Despite its eventual evasiveness, its representation and conceptual storage fosters the relative explicitness of what the speaker expresses about her attitudes, feelings and emotions.

Support of this alternative account may be found in the fact that expressive expletives can additionally behave like intensifiers such as *very*, *highly*, *rather* or *fairly*, and like adverbs such as *extremely*, *incredibly*, *surprisingly* or *shockingly*. While such intensifiers increase the gradable quality or property denoted by an adjective, or the manner referred to by another adverb, those adverbs do not solely upgrade qualities, properties or manners, but also convey further nuances linked to personal states such as amazement, incredulity, surprise, shock, unexpectedness, puzzlement or many others that can hardly be paraphrased or pinned down in conceptual terms:

(11)a. The steak was fucking raw.

b. Peter came fucking late.

When expressive expletives co-occur with qualifying adjectives or adverbs and behave in this fashion, they may likewise be hypothesised to enact lexical pragmatic processes resulting in more specific conceptual representations of the quality or manner alluded to by those words (Author, In press a). Thus, the expletive in (11a) could give rise to RAW* denoting a higher degree of rawness or a type of rawness beyond average, but also a

disappointing, irritating, unbearable or unexpected type of rawness, or even perhaps a kind of rawness that can hardly be described by means of words and which the hearer is therefore invited to figure out. Similarly, in (11b) the expletive would contribute to the modulation of LATE as LATE* as a way of capturing a lateness that perhaps exceeds decency standards or some sort of exasperating, distressing, disturbing or worrisome lateness. In both cases, nevertheless, the resulting fine-tuned concepts might harbour information about the speaker's psychological states.

Summing up, the target of the attitude that expressive expletives verbalise is the referent of the nominal head that they accompany, which is adjusted on the grounds of the attitudinal information that they make manifest. The following section addresses why other referents, or even the entire state of affairs alluded to in the sentence, may be felt to be the target of the speaker's attitude.

4.2 On the expression of attitudes towards another referent and the propositional content

Considerations about cognitive efficiency and communicative abilities rule out the possibility that the attitude conveyed by an expressive expletive is expressed about the referent of another non-adjacent constituent or even the state of affairs referred to in the sentence hosting the expletive. For either or both of these to be perceived as the target of the speaker's attitude, other elements showing psychological states need to be produced. Some of them are fully linguistic and their interpretation involves decoding and inference: attitudinal adverbials headed by adverbs like *happily* or *sadly* (Ifantidou 1992). Others are on the verge of the linguistic and non-linguistic, and their interpretation requires inference and perhaps decoding in those cases in which they are conventionally associated with a particular state: interjections (Wharton 2003, 2009;

Author 2009a, 2009b). Others, in contrast, are vocal and kinetic signals that fall within the category of paralinguistic: prosodic features like pitch, lexical and contrastive stress, tones, tempo or rhythm, and facial expressions, gestures or poses (Wilson & Wharton 2006; Wharton 2009, 2012). Depending on their (in)determinacy and explicitness, their interpretation may in some cases demand a considerable amount of inferential work (Sperber & Wilson 2015) and be accomplished analogically, by taking into account modifications in their characteristics motivated by the psychological state triggering them (Wharton 2012: 122). Consequently, their contribution cannot be finitely paraphrased or amount to just one proposition, but may be an open-ended array of propositions or even non-propositional effects like images or feelings (Wilson & Carston 2019). In other cases, their stabilisation and conventionalisation to convey information about a particular psychological state causes the evidence exhibited by paralinguistic elements to be more indirect and their interpretation to also involve a certain amount of decoding (Wilson & Wharton 2006; Wharton 2009, 2012, 2016).

In relevance-theoretic pragmatics, attitudinal adverbials, interjections and paralinguistic are argued to contribute to higher-level explicatures describing the speaker's attitude towards the communicated content by signalling the type of attitude that she expresses. Such explicatures are superordinate to the pragmatically enriched propositional form, or the lower-level explicature of an utterance, so these linguistic and paralinguistic elements may be said to take that proposition under their scope (Wilson & Sperber 1993; Wilson & Wharton 2006; Wharton 2009, 2012). Accordingly, the occurrence of an item belonging to the first two groups in a sentence including an expressive expletive could clearly indicate that the speaker has a particular attitude towards the whole proposition that it communicates, encourage the hearer to create a mental representation of that attitude and somehow guide him in so doing:

(12)a. Fuck/Unfortunately, my friend has invited his damn(ed) girlfriend!

b. [The speaker is angry/disappointed that [his friend has invited his damn(ed) girlfriend]]

Concerning intonation, relevance-theoretic pragmatics characterises English tones as follows (Clark 2007):

- Falling tones indicate that the proposition expressed counts as a description of a state of affairs.
- Falling and rising tones mark that the proposition expressed is presented as an interpretation of some other individual's thought.
- Rising-falling tones exhibit the speaker's surprise, irritation, disappointment, etc., at a proposition that is expressed as a description of a state of affairs or an interpretation of somebody else's thoughts.
- Falling-rising tones instruct the hearer to regard the proposition expressed as an interpretation of the thoughts entertained or of a description of a state of affairs made by another individual.
- Level tones indicate the incompleteness of an utterance.

In turn, while lexical and contrastive stress are considered to fulfil a highlighting function, pitch is regarded as an overt display of the speaker's psychological state (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995; Wilson & Wharton 2006; Wharton 2009, 2012). And something similar happens with language-like gestures like head nods, raised eyebrows, finger and head pointing or grimaces, to name but some. The fact that the speaker is thought to express a particular attitude towards the entire propositional content that she communicates by means of a sentence where an expressive expletive occurs may be due

to any of these prosodic clues, which may similarly result in specific higher-level explicatures.

However, a specific pitch, contrastive and lexical stress, tempo, facial expression and/or language-like gesture may be intentionally and overtly produced upon the utterance of a particular sentential constituent. Instead of affecting the whole utterance of the sentence where an expressive expletive appears, the effect of that paralinguistic clue would be restricted to the referent of that constituent and amount to an adjustment of its conceptual representation on the basis of the attitudinal information made manifest by that clue. In other words, specific purposeful and ostensive paralinguistic features, individually or jointly produced, could also give rise to lexical pragmatic processes resulting in narrowed conceptual representations whose encyclopaedic entries would be enriched with propositional or non-propositional information about the attitude attributed to the speaker (Author, Submitted). Accordingly, a grimace of disgust or irritation, pitch highness, additional articulatory strength, slowed down rate of delivery and perhaps a closed punch vigorously moving downwards could provide GIRLRIEND in (1) above with information pertaining to the speaker's negative attitude towards the person in question. Therefore, the fact that a speaker is considered to have a particular attitude towards the referent of a constituent other than the one by which an expressive expletive is placed may be the consequence of the intentional and overt production of (a) certain paralinguistic feature(s), which would enable the representation of the speaker's attitude as part of the specification of the conceptual material activated by that constituent.

5 Conclusion

The extant pragmatic and syntactic approaches to expressive expletives posit that the attitude that these words verbalise may be perceived to be held towards the referent of a different constituent from that next to which they are placed or even towards the state of affairs alluded to in the sentence hosting them. This paper has proposed an alternative pragmatic, relevance-theoretic account that argues, on the grounds of considerations about cognitive effort and communicative efficiency, that the target of that attitude can only be the referent of the sentential constituent that they accompany. This account suggests that expressive expletives make manifest propositional and non-propositional information about such an attitude, which contributes to conceptual specification. Since attitudinal information enriches the logical and/or encyclopaedic entries of the concept activated by that constituent, that information is represented and stored at a conceptual level as a by-product of the lexical pragmatic processes responsible for that lexical pragmatic process. Finally, this account shows that other attitude-related effects may be the result of a variety of linguistic and paralinguistic elements that are specialised in making manifest attitudinal information, as well as in enacting its representation as higher-level explicatures or context-sensitive conceptual entities.

All in all, this account evidences that considering pragmatic factors and the mechanisms at work during comprehension may contribute to unravelling the communicative effects of linguistic elements like expressive expletives. Relevance theory (Sperber & Wilson 1986/1995; Wilson & Sperber 2002, 2004) offers a cognitive model wherein ostensive intentional input and the constant search for efficiency greatly determine the output of the tasks that these mechanisms carry out, our understanding of which has no doubt been significantly widened by the most inspiring work done by Deirdre Wilson. The role that this model assigns to certain linguistic and paralinguistic

elements, as well as the adjustments and attitudinal representations that they trigger, avoid accounting for the attitude-related effects of expressive expletives by resorting to the accomplishment of an independent speech act or to a syntactic feature that needs to be detached from them, thus enabling a variety of syntactic hops and movements.

Just as the target of the attitude voiced by expressive expletives has been the subject of much debate, it would be illuminating to explore if the psychological states made manifest by other linguistic elements, like evidential adverbs and adverbials, are perceived as expressed about distinct sentential constituents or even the state of affairs mentioned in the sentence hosting them. If they were, perhaps future research could address the effects of these elements along the lines of the account proposed in this paper. It would be interesting to check if, in addition to constraining higher-level explicatures, they could also give rise to fine-tuned, occasion-specific conceptual representations capturing attitudinal information.

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